

REVIEW OF THE CONCEPT OF ASHAYAPAKARSHA & ITS UTILITY IN AYURVEDA

*¹Vikas Saini, ²Shalini Panwar, ³Nitin Sharma

*^{1,2}Department of Ayurved Samhita Evam Siddhant, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda, Roorkee.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Rog Nidan, Dev Bhoomi Medical College of Ayurveda and Hospital, Dehradun, UK.

Article Received on 29 March 2026,

Article Revised on 18 April 2026,

Article Published on 01 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19877336>

*Corresponding Author

Vikas Saini

Department of Ayurved Samhita Evam
Siddhant, Quadra Institute of
Ayurveda, Roorkee.

How to cite this Article: *¹Vikas Saini, ²Shalini Panwar, ³Nitin Sharma (2026). Review Of The Concept Of Ashayapakarsha & Its Utility In Ayurveda. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(5), 255-260.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, The Ancient *Veda* of life i.e. states that *Sharira* is comprised of *Dosha*, *Dhatu*, *Mala* and *Indriya*.^[1] *Nidan* (causative factors), *Tridoshas*, *Dushya* (*Dhatu*, *Upadhatu* and *Mala*) and *Agni* are the essential elements for the commencement of a *vyadhi*. A unique kind of Principle that falls under *Dosha Bheda Hetu* is *Ashayapakarsha*, mentioned elaborately by *Acharya Charak*. *Nidan*, the external vitiating factor, along with *Dosha* and *Dushya*, even if limited in number, the manifested diseases are innumerable because of variation in the *Samprapti* (pathogenesis). Although, the progression of a disease is not guaranteed by the mere existence of *Nidan*, *Dosha* and *Dushya*. The progression of a *vyadhi* is merely variable as it depends on the number of the factors. Sometimes when these factors are present in a vitiated

condition then also disease may not occur or occurs late or occurs with few symptoms or symptoms are present in a subtle form. Hence a detailed study of the this unique concept of *Ashayapakarsha* will aid a better understanding regarding the *samprapti* of *vyadhi*, its *vighatan* and planning the treatment accordingly.

KEYWORDS: *Dosha Bheda*, *vyadhi*, *Hetu*, *Samprapti*, Innumerable.

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda*, *Panch nidan* is composed of *Nidan*, *Purvroop*, *Roop*, *Samprapti* and *Upshaya*.^[2]

All of these are vital tools for understanding the vyadhi (disease). Specifically, out of these *Nidan* is the most important tool. For the *Chikitsa* it has been said that ‘*Sanshepta Kriyayogo Nidan Parivarjanam*’ which also indicates the importance of *Nidan* in *Chikitsa*.^[3] As the *Ayurveda* i.e the *Upaveda* of *Atharveda*, is full of *Siddhanth* (Principles) based on the *ansha-ansh kalpana* of *Doshas*. *Ayurveda* has considered that the balanced state of *Dosha*, *Dhatu* and *Mala* leads to state of health and their imbalanced state results into the progression the *vyadhi* in the body.^[4] In this manner, understanding all the core concepts and Principles of *Ayurveda* definitely makes *Chikitsa* of *vyadhi* much simpler. *Ashayapakarsha* is one of such principles and this article is an attempt to better understand regarding this old aged importance of this *Siddhanth* of *Ayurveda*.

This concept can be understood minutely by the knowledge about the site and movement of *Doshas*. *Acharya Vagbhata* specifies the place of each and every *Dosha*, i.e *Pakwashaya* for *Vata dosha*, *Nabhi* for *Pitta dosha* and *Ura Pradesh* for *Kapha dosha*. *Acharya Charak* specified the site of *tridosha*, i.e *Pakwashaya* for *Vata dosha*, *Aamashya* for *Pitta dosha* and *Ura Pradesh* for *Kapha dosha*.^[5] And *Acharya Sushruta* has mentioned as *Shroni Guda*, *Aamashya Madhya* and *Pakwashya* the site for *tridoshas*.

Table 1: Specific site of *Tridoshas* as per different *Acharya*.

	<i>Acharya Charak</i>	<i>Acharya Sushruta</i>	<i>Acharya Vagbhata</i>
<i>Vata Dosha</i>	<i>Pakwashaya</i>	<i>Shroni Guda</i>	<i>Pakwashaya</i>
<i>Pitta Dosha</i>	<i>Aamashya</i>	<i>Aamashya Madhya</i>	<i>Nabhi</i>
<i>Kapha Dosha</i>	<i>Ura Pradesh</i>	<i>Pakwashya</i>	<i>Ura Pradesh</i>

Movement of *Dosha* i.e. *sanchaya*, *prakopa* and *prasara* in the healthy individual, varies as per the *Ritu*, *Kaal* and when it does not influence much to form the diseases are called the *Prakrita Gati* of *Dosha*. But sometimes due to *Dosha prakopak hetu*, *Doshas* get vitiated which moves from their place and known as the *Vikrita Dosha Gati*. It hampers the health of an individual, causes an imbalance in the equilibrium of *Doshas* and ultimately leads to the *Vyadhi*. *Vikrita Dosha Gati* can be *Urdhwa*, *Adha*, *Tiryak*, *Koshthashrita*, *Shakhashrita* as per the direction and movement of *Dosha* in the body.^[6]

Acharya Charak has explained in *sutra sthana* a very unique concept regarding the pathogenesis of disease i.e, “*Ashayapakarsha*” in *Charak Samhita*, *sutra sthana* 17.^[7] The *Sanskrit* word ‘*Ashayaaaparsha*’ includes two words- ‘*Ashyaya*’ meaning a space or site and ‘*Apakarsha*’, meaning to draw off or take away. Thus, the word *Ashayapakarsha* means taking

away from one's site. Based on the *Sthanika Doshas*, the *lakashan* can be seen in the *sharira*. The concept of *Ashayapakarsha* is based on the Permutations and Combinations of *Doshas*. Also, *Ashayapakarsha* is explained in detail in *Madhukosha's* commentary in the context of *Dosha gati*.

For the *Vata Dosha* it has been said by *Acharya Sharangdhar* that '*pittam pangu kapham pangu pangavo mala dhatavah vayuna yatra niyanteta tatra gacchanti meghavat*' which means *Pitta*, *Kapha*, *Mala* and *Dhatu* are lame without *Vata*.^[8] If *Vata* is vitiated then the whole controlling system and normal functioning of *Dosha*, *Dhatu*, *Mala* will be hampered leading to innumerable manifestations of the diseases of *Sharir*, *Indriya*, and *Manas*. Also, *Vata* is primarily responsible for all the movements and activities in the body because of the *Yogavaahi*, *Shushma*, *Chala*, *Laghu guna* of it.^[9]

Additionally in *Charak Samhita*, *Acharya* has also cited that '*Sarva he chesta vaten sa pranah pradina smrita, tenaeve roga jayente ten chevoparudhyte*'.^[10] As a result of these *gunas*, *Vata* when vitiated goes to the site of *Dosha*, which are in normal *sthana* and their normal *pramana* performing normal function takes them away (*Apkarshana*) from the *sthana* (*Ashya*) and manifests the disease.

METHOD

As a source, various *Ayurvedic* classics such as *Charak Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Madhav Nidan*, *Sharangdhar Samhita* and Modern literature were consulted. In addition to this, various peer-reviewed research journals and published research papers have been studied. Various electronic data bases, including PubMed, Google Scholar and *Ayurvedic* specific databases were systematically searched for relevant articles, research papers, books and scholarly publications.

RESULT

Vata Dosha holds normal *kriya* of *Srotas*, *Dhatu*, *Mala* & *Kostha* in the *Sharira*. The normal *Vata Dosha* moving in the body performs the function by making gross and subtle channels. Vitiation of *Vata Dosha* in the body impacts the other *Doshas* as it creates *Aavarana*,^[11] *Ashayapakarsha* over them which over time leads to variety *vyadhis*.

DISCUSSION

The fate of a disease depends upon many factors such as *Dosha*, *Dushya*, *Agni* and *Bala* of the

person. The unique principle of *Ashyaapkarsh* provides a better picture of the level of *Dosha* and its *Gati*. In the context of *Vyadhi*, the concept of *Ashyaapkarsh* helps to understand its pathogenesis. And additionally beneficial for planning the treatment. It can be understood in the following manner in the context of the diseases-

1. *Sheetapitta*

Sheetapitta is a *Tridoshaj twacha shrita vyadhi* explained by *Acharya Madhav* in *Madhav nidan adhyaya* 50. In this *vyadhi*, *Sheeta marutadi nidan* leads to the *Prakopa* of *Vata* and *Kaphaj doshas* which unite with the *Pitta dosha*.^[12] It then drives *Pitta dosha* (*bhajak pitta*, *ranjak pitta*) from its *sthanika pradesha*. This results in the *shotha*, *kandu*, *jwar* and *vidaha* like *lakshana* in the *twachadi aashya* and that is called the *Sheetapitta*.^[13]

Flow chart 1-Involvement of *Vata* in the *Samprapti* of *Sheetapitta*

2. *Shakhashrita Kamala*

Acharya Charakhas given a brief description of *Shakhashrita Kamala* in *Chikitsa sthana* 16.^[14] The prime cause of its occurrence is the obstruction of *Sthanika Dosha* i.e, *Pitta* by the *Vata* and *Kapha*, which is as follows- *Nidan* such as *Guru*, *Sheeta*, *Ruksha*, *Swadu Aahar* and *Vega Dharan* causes the aggravation of *Vata* and *Kaphaj Dosha* in the body. As the *Vata* is predominantly involved in the movement of *doshas* and also it governs the functions in the body too. *Vata* here obstructs the natural pathway of *Pitta dosha* and drives it away from its normal *sthana* (site).

Flow chart 2-Involvement of *Vata* in the *Sampriti* of *Shakhashrita Kamala*

Guru, Sheeta, Ruksha, Swadu (Aaharaj nidan), and Vega Dharan (Viharaj nidan)

Here, Vitiated *Vata* drives normal *Pitta* from its *sthanika aashyaya* and in this manner leads to the *Shakhashrita Kamala*.

3. *Vataj Atisara*

Due to *Ruksha, Alpa, Pramitashansa & Atapa Sevan* as a *nidan*, it causes *vata prakopa* which hampers the *agni* and the *Jaleeyaamasha* is not metabolized properly in turn leading to *Jaleeya Vridhi* in the *sharira*. *Jaleeya amsha* is in the form of *mutra* and *sweda*. The vitiated *vata* takes *mutra* from *basti* and *sweda* from *meda* to the *pureeshashyas* and cause *Vataj atisara*.

CONCLUSION

For the right *Pareeksha* (Diagnosis) of any *vyadhi*, it needs the basic knowledge regarding the *Doshas*, their *Sthana* and *Gati*. Identification of *Sthanika Dosha* and *Agantuja Dosha* is also necessary. *Vata* is the prime cause of *Ashayapkarsha*. Better understanding of this old aged concept including the *Dosha Sthananatara Gamana*, helps the *Chikitsak* to better plan the treatment. That's why it has been said by *Acharya Charak* that '*Rogam aado parikshet tato antaram aaustham*'^[15] means *Pariksha* is very much essential before starting any treatment. *Upashaya* and *Anupashaya* can help to diagnose and plan treatment. Hence, the concept of *Ashayapkarsha* is practically evident, unique yet challenging.

REFERENCES

1. Sushrute Samhita, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Reprint edition 2017, sutra sthana 15/3, Page no. 73.

2. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2015, nidan sthana 1/6, Page no. 601.
3. Sushrute Samhita, uttar tantra, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Reprint edition 2017, sutra sthana 9/4, Page no. 184.
4. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2014, sutra sthana 20/8, Page no. 296.
5. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2015, sutra sthana 20/8, Page no. 296.
6. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2015, sutra sthana 11/48, Page no. 235.
7. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Varanasi, Reprint edition 2015, sutra sthana 17/45-46, Page no. 343.
8. Sharangdhar, Sharangdhar samhita, Varanasi, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishtan; 2017, Vol I, sutra sthana 12, verse 7, Page no. 185.
9. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2015, sutra sthana 1/59, Page no. 36.
10. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2015, sutra sthana 17/118, Page no. 366.
11. Charak Samhita-Uttarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2016, chikitsa sthana 28/60, Page no.788.
12. Madav nidanam, Madhukosha vyakhaya vibhushitam Part II, Chaukhamba Prakashan, Varanasi, Reprint edition 2021, Chapter 50/1, Page no. 200.
13. Madav nidanam, Madhukosha vyakhaya vibhushitam Part II, Chaukhamba Prakashan, Varanasi, Reprint edition 2021, Chapter 50/3-4, Page no. 201.
14. Charak Samhita-Uttarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2016, chikitsa sthana 16/125, Page no.505.
15. Charak Samhita-Purvarthe, Chaukhambha Bharati Academy Varanasi, Reprint edition 2015, sutra sthana 20/20, Page no. 406.